

INTERACTION OF SCIENCE AND SOCIETY IN BARBARA KINGSOLVER'S FLIGHT BEHAVIOUR

Jumanazar Niyozov

Teacher at UzSWLU

jumanazarnf@gmail.com

Annotation. The last 20 years have seen a sharp rise in the production of climate fiction, or cli-fi. It is crucial to keep researching how climate change is portrayed in fiction and what this can indicate about how people view the problem and our future, since the subject grows more pressing every year. Therefore, by examining how science and society interact in Barbara's cli-fi novel Flight Behavior, particularly through the scientist character, this paper aims to add to the continuing discussion in climate fiction. This work comes to the conclusion that the novel shows how society and science are inseparable and that both are necessary to comprehend climate change in fiction.

Key words: climate fiction, cli-fi, climate change, global warming, ecocriticism, the Anthropocene.

Introduction. Climate change fiction has recently emerged as a literary phenomenon with its own buzzword: cli-fi. Climate change fiction or cli-fi as it is affectionately known, is one of the most successful new genres of Anglophone fiction and though the exact origins of climate fiction are vague, massive credit is given to Dan Bloom for coining the term 'cli-fi'. [5] Likewise, Svoboda asserts that the term 'cli-fi' was coined in 2007 by Taiwan-based blogger, Dan Bloom, and it notably refers to literary works which deal with climate change [10., pp. 43-54]. The neologism, cli-fi, denotes novels, short stories and films whose main focus is on the consequences of global warming. According to Johns-Putra, climate change has arisen as a prevailing theme in literature, and respectively, in literature studies during the last couple of years and its popularity has given rise to the term cli-fi. Climate change fiction works reflect and intensify the scientific data and patterns of the climate change phenomenon from the global discourse, thus according to Trexler, this literary genre attempts to circumvent the closeness between climate change scientific facts and those depicted in fiction. Thus, what is depicted in cli-fi works may not necessarily be an exact reflection of how natural climate change and anthropogenic changes might occur in reality.

Methodology. Ecocriticism may appear to be the evident academic approach to climate fiction, but the field has been accused of not sufficiently engaging with climate change in the past. The dominant definition, as written by Cheryll Glotfelty, defines ecocriticism as “the study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment.” [1. p. xviii] Robert Kern elaborates on this definition, stating that ecocriticism is a literary theory “designed to expose and facilitate analysis of a text’s orientation both to the world it imagines and to the world in which it takes shape,” in its quest to advocate for the environment. [7] These definitions illustrate the focus on nature and its relationship to literature that are the core pillars of ecocriticism.

Publications of climate fiction flourished and changed the ways in which such fiction is analysed, leading to a shift away from ecocriticism towards a separate critical theory for climate fiction. Trexler and Johns-Putra show that ecocriticism shifted to incorporate climate change in its analyses as of 2010. [12., pp. 185-200] This, in turn, created a subfield within ecocriticism. Johns-Putra explores these developments in an updated article, demonstrating that cli-fi was “being heralded as a discrete subfield of literary studies.” [6., p. 266] It now focused on analysing cli-fi in terms of its educational abilities at one end, and analysing the representation of climate change in fiction at the other. This marks a significant shift in literary theory towards an understanding of how climate change should be analysed. Trexler in his book *Anthropocene Fictions* analyses that cli-fi is rooted in the Anthropocene, which emphasises both the natural processes of climate change and humanity’s role in global warming, which has exponentially increased climate change since the Victorian era. In this context, Trexler highlights the cultural significance of climate change, arguing that “recognising global warming requires more than assenting to scientific data.” [14., p. 5] Instead, he claims that cli-fi is an accumulation of several aspects. Trexler therefore argues in favour of analysing cli-fi in its own context as a separate critical theory. This is a significant development in the analysis of cli-fi and provides the foundation for analysing how the critical theory of cli-fi operates, as will be explored later in this chapter.

Result and Discussions. *Flight Behaviour* illustrates several perspectives on climate change that are determined by the social contexts of the characters. Haynes points out that “the larger-scale issue of climate change and why it is resisted by so many is debated vigorously between characters of diverse background.” [4., pp. 139-140] Goodbody captures Kingsolver’s intentions behind her use of these various perspectives, stating that “personalising the experience of global warming and

dramatizing its consequences,” is her way of confronting the reader with climate change and making the future imaginable. [3., p. 42] Kingsolver emphasises three perspectives on climate change, namely the scientific perspective of Ovid Byron and his team, the anthropocentric perspective of the local community, and Dellarobia, who eventually comes to be positioned in the middle. The local community of Feathertown are poor, religious farmers, who do not care much for ‘proper’ education. Dellarobia explains to Ovid that “they don’t need it for life around here. College is kind of irrelevant.” [8., p. 308] The locals’ social position determines their views on climate change. Climate concerns do not tend to find particularly fertile ground, in such rural areas, as climate change is overshadowed by poverty in these places. Lloyd and Rapson identify the anthropocentric nature of the locals’ views, highlighting “the Tennessee farming communities’ exploitation of geographical features for profit.” [9., p. 920] This is reflected in the novel when Dellarobia explains that the locals “think nature will organise itself around what suits them.” [8., p. 314] Dellarobia’s in-laws hardly consider the consequences of their logging plans. In addition, Goodbody argues that “religion emerges as a form of denial.” [3., p. 55] When confronted with floods and irregular weather patterns, the blame is on God. However, Kingsolver is not criticising them. As Lloyd and Rapson point out, Dellarobia demonstrates “sympathy for those who are sceptical about climate change,” [9., p. 920] as she explains that “people are scared to face up to a bad outcome. That’s just human.” [8., p. 318] Kingsolver thus seems to position the blame more on their situation than on the people themselves. However, Kingsolver makes sure to emphasise the limitations of their views by illustrating their ignorance of climate change that could have horrible consequences.

The character of Dellarobia stands out against the local community, which provides the foundation for her eventual partnership with Dr Ovid Byron. The novel continuously illustrates that Dellarobia does not fit into her community. Tabak argues that “Dellarobia first believes the monarchs to be a gift from God – which, unlike climate change, she believes in.” [11., p. 99] Upon seeing the butterflies without her glasses, Dellarobia describes them as “a lake of fire, something far more fierce and wondrous than either of those elements alone. The impossible.” [8., p. 22] Dellarobia is overcome by this image in the forest that appears at precisely the right time, preventing her from making a mistake by cheating on her husband. For a moment, she considers it to be the divine. However, in contrast to her community, Dellarobia often expresses scepticism about her religion: “she and Jesus weren’t that close.” [8., p. 19] Goodbody explains that “Dellarobia conforms to social expectation by going to

the local church on Sunday, but maintains a rebellious stance of sceptical detachment.” [3., p. 55] Her perception of God is different as she explains her belief “that everything else is in motion while God does not move at all.” [8., p. 484] Dellarobia is also significantly more aware of climate change than her community. The locals see the weather disruptions as an act of God, but Dellarobia is aware of climate change: “Climate change, she knew to be wary of that.” [8., p. 202] Furthermore, as Goodbody points out, Dellarobia understands the emotional comfort of religion, but “recognises it as part of the problem of our blindness to climate change.” [3., p. 55] The arrival of Ovid Byron only enhances these realisations, as will be explored later. Dellarobia’s unique position within her community is further emphasised when she tells Ovid that she “was the only one in my class to try for college.” [8., p. 314] These examples demonstrate Dellarobia’s unique position in her community that allow her to be open to change. As a result, Dellarobia is the least limited in her perspective in comparison to the other characters.

The arrival of Dr Ovid Byron marks a shift in the novel, opening the topic of climate change to the scientific perspective. Ovid Byron is an entomologist, who takes his work to Feathertown once the butterflies have settled there. Trexler describes the role of the scientist “as either Earth-saving heroes or minor characters that allow the author to dump masses of data on the reader.” [15., p. 47] While Ovid does take on the role of a teacher and mentor to Dellarobia, Kingsolver does an excellent job in preventing information dumps on the reader by dispersing the scientific facts across several instances of dialogue with Dellarobia. Haynes observes this as well, stating that the dialogue between them allows for information to “be delivered in small packets in response to specific incidents and questions.” [4., p. 139] However, Dr Byron does not fit into the ‘hero’ category either. Haynes points out Ovid’s portrayal “as dedicated to his research task of measuring the dislocated monarch butterflies’ response to an alien climate but clinically detached.” [4., p. 134] As a scientist, Ovid must be objective and focus on the facts only. Throughout the novel, Ovid regularly reminds Dellarobia of this fact. At the early stages of their partnership, he explains “we are scientists. Our job here is only to describe what exists.” [8., p. 204] Dellarobia describes him as “a man possessed with purpose,” [8., p. 191] who insists that he cannot serve as a physician or superhero as “we are only scientists.” [8., p. 315] Despite his insistence on scientific objectivity, Ovid does have an emotional side to him. He addresses this on occasions when Dellarobia is floored by his objectivity: “But we are also human. We like these butterflies, you know?” [8., p. 204] However, his scientific nature maintains the upper hand. Ovid’s insistence on

objectivity prevents him from making an actual difference. As the local community is limited in their perspective as products of the society they live in, Ovid is limited in his views due to his exclusively scientific approach. Thus, Kingsolver emphasises the limitations of these separate perspectives when they refuse to interact. However, Dellarobia and Ovid's partnership changes these headstrong perspectives.

The scientist perspective of Ovid Byron and the emotional, non-scientist perspective of Dellarobia Turnbow change each other throughout the novel. The novel often emphasises the differences between Dellarobia and Ovid, highlighting the assumptive divide between science and society. This is evidenced by Dellarobia's embarrassment in her interactions with the scientists. Her embarrassment is present in their first interaction when she invites Ovid to have dinner with her family, where she explains the butterfly species to the specialist. Upon finding out he is, in fact, a scientist and butterfly expert, "Dellarobia felt numb. Hoodwinked, embarrassed, furious, entranced." [8., p. 165] This embarrassment persists in her continuous interactions with the scientists as she feels "embarrassed to invite these people into her house," [8., p. 212] even after getting close to them. Dellarobia points out this divide herself, describing it as "there were two worlds here, behaving as if their own was all that mattered." [8., p. 209] This divide is also clearly noticeable in the dialogue between Ovid and Dellarobia. In their conversations, Ovid's objectivity as a scientist is consistently emphasised: "Science doesn't tell us what we should do. It only tells us what is." [8., p. 442] Dellarobia eventually challenges Ovid's objectivity with her own perspective; one that is comprised of emotion and humanity. In response to his insistence on science remaining objective, she retorts "that must be why people don't like it." [8., p. 442] Her disapproval of science's passive interaction with climate change is most clearly captured when Ovid states "I'm not here to save the monarchs," to which she replies, "if you're not, who is?" [8., p. 442] Goodbody explains that "in Dellarobia's world of 'little hopes' and thankfulness when short-term targets are reached, there is no room for Byron's bouts of pessimism." [3., p. 49] The interactions between Dellarobia and Ovid slowly but steadily allow for a mutual influence on one another. Tabak argues that Dellarobia's knowledge of climate change is triggered by Ovid's teachings. This is not entirely true as Dellarobia was previously aware of climate change. However, Tabak is right in stating that Ovid plays a fundamental role in Dellarobia's understanding of science and climate change. He is the one who teaches her scientific facts, facilitating Dellarobia's "inner journey from ignorance and absence of concern to scientific understanding." [3., p. 50] This, Goodbody argues, is also because of "her curiosity and her willingness to

read and learn.” [3., p. 55] Due to Ovid’s influence and her curious nature, “Dellarobia’s perspective has undergone a fundamental shift.”¹⁵¹ Dellarobia’s non-scientific, emotional perspective also influences Ovid’s views. This is most evident when he asks Dellarobia “what was the use of saving a world that had no soul left in it.” [8., p. 438] His confession that “these were not scientific thoughts,” [8., p. 438] directly shows Dellarobia’s influence on his perspective. At the end of the novel, both have changed due to their partnership and have exceeded the previous limitations that confined their perspectives.

Through the relationship between Ovid Byron and Dellarobia, Kingsolver suggests that climate change can only be understood when considered from the perspectives of both science and society. Trexler argues that climate change and its fictional manifestations are the accumulation of science and society. [15., p. 72] This idea constitutes the theoretical framework of cli-fi, and *Flight Behaviour* suits it nicely. As the paper has shown, the interactions between Ovid and Dellarobia eventually leads to a change in them both. While Dellarobia becomes acquainted with science and learns to understand climate change in factual terms, Ovid’s objectivity is challenged, and his more emotional side is brought out. Dellarobia eventually leaves her unfulfilling marriage and pursues a college education to become a scientist herself. She has not, however, abandoned her identity, which partially follows from the social context of the local community in which she lives. Lloyd and Rapson affirm this by emphasising Kingsolver’s awareness “of our human investment in the fragility of the ‘natural world’,” that is combined with her interest in science. [9., p. 926] This is reflected in Dellarobia, who retains her emotional side and lived experiences in poverty and religion as she pursues an education. As a result, Dellarobia serves as an intermediary, which symbolises the interaction of science and society. The novel highlights several occasions that, according to Lloyd and Rapson, are “typical of Dellarobia’s attempts to mediate between the concerns of nonscientists (local community) to the scientists.” [9., p. 920] Even before she decides to pursue science herself, Dellarobia acts as a mediator between these two worlds. This is visible, for example, when she attempts to explain the locals’ mistrust of the science team to Ovid: “These positions get assigned to people,” [8., p. 445] or when she tries to explain to her husband why the butterflies are not the gift from God, they would like to believe they are: “The butterflies are all going to die.” [8., p. 353] This, in addition to the mutual influence between Ovid and Dellarobia, supports the notion that it is essential to combine science and society in order to understand climate change. Ovid’s character is also an important aspect of this analysis. Trexler studies

Dr Byron as “an imperfect vessel of climatic truth, conveying the limits of science in the contemporary world.” [13., p. 227] His objectivity prevents him from making an actual difference in the natural world that he loves. Dellarobia’s shock at this symbolises Kingsolver’s critical stance on the role of science and further establishes her message that science and society need to interact with one another to fully grasp climate change.

Conclusion. Kingsolver offers a hopeful account of the future of society with her demonstration that humanity is capable of change. Without fundamental changes in humanity’s energy consumption, climate change will end in catastrophe. Kingsolver employs this emotional technique through Dellarobia and visualises her faith in humanity’s ability to change by having Dellarobia find her agency. The end of the novel shows Dellarobia’s decision to leave her husband and pursue a college education. Her decision to attend college requires her to move to the nearby city, where her children will likewise spend most of their time. In this sense, Dellarobia and her children are also moving to a new world. Dellarobia’s old life has vanished to the point of no return, but it has led to a new and better life. Kingsolver thus offers a vision of hope with her belief that humanity is capable of change. When science and society interact with one another to fully comprehend climate change and seek innovation, we move towards a new and better world.

References:

1. Glotfelty, Cheryll, and Harold Fromm, eds. *The Ecocriticism Reader: Landmarks in Literary Ecology*. Athens: University of Georgia Press, 1996.
2. Goodbody, Axel, and Adeline Johns-Putra. “The Rise of the Climate Change Novel.” In *Climate and Literature* edited by Adeline Johns-Putra, 229-245. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108505321.015>.
3. Goodbody, Axel. “Risk, Denial and Narrative Form in Climate Change Fiction: Barbara Kingsolver’s *Flight* Behavior and Ilija Trojanow’s *Melting Ice*.” In *The Anticipation of Catastrophe: Environmental Risk in North American Literature and Culture*, edited by S. Mayer and A. Weik von Mossner, 39-58. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2014.
4. Haynes, Roslynn D. “Bringing Science into Fiction.” *Zeitschrift für Anglistik und Amerikanistik* 64, no. 2 (2016): 127-148. <https://doi.org/10.1515/zaa-2016-0015>.

5. Irr, C. (2017). "Climate fiction in English." Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/35288142/Climate_Fiction_in_English
6. Johns-Putra, Adeline. "Climate Change in Literature and Literary Studies: From Cli-Fi, Climate Change Theater and Ecopoetry to Ecocriticism and Climate Change Criticism." *WIREs Climate Change* 7, no. 2 (2016): 266-282. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.385>.
7. Kern, Robert. "Ecocriticism: What Is It Good For?" *Interdisciplinary Studies in Literature and Environment* 7, no. 1 (2000): 9-32. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44087363>.
8. Kingsolver, Barbara. *Flight Behaviour*. London: Faber and Faber, 2013. First published 2012 by HarperCollins Inc.
9. Lloyd, Christopher, and Jessica Rapson. "'Family territory' to the 'circumference of the earth': local and planetary memories of climate change in Barbara Kingsolver's *Flight Behaviour*." *Textual Practice* 31, no. 5 (2017): 911-931. doi=10.1080/0950236X.2017.1323487.
10. Svoboda, M. (2016). Cli-fi on the screen(s): Patterns in the representations of climate change in fictional films. *WIREs Climate Change*, 7(43), 43-64.
11. Tabak, Eline D. "Science in Fiction: A Brief Look at Communicating Climate Change through the Novel." *RCC Perspectives*, no. 4 (2019): 97-104. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26760170>.
12. Trexler, Adam, and Adeline Johns-Putra. "Climate Change in Literature and Literary Criticism." *WIREs Climate Change* 2, no. 2 (2011): 185-200. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.105>.
13. Trexler, Adam. "CONCLUSION: The Real and the Future." In *Anthropocene Fictions: The Novel in a Time of Climate Change*, 223-237. University of Virginia Press, 2015. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt13x1r99.9>.
14. Trexler, Adam. "INTRODUCTION: Contextualizing the Climate Change Novel." In *Anthropocene Fictions: The Novel in a Time of Climate Change*, 1-28. University of Virginia Press, 2015. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt13x1r99.4>.
15. Trexler, Adam. "TRUTH: Science, Culture, and Construction." In *Anthropocene Fictions: The Novel in a Time of Climate Change*, 29-74. University of Virginia Press, 2015. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt13x1r99.5>.
16. Urry, John. "Climate Change and Society." In *Why the Social Sciences Matter*, edited by Jonathan Michie and Cary L. Cooper, 45-59. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137269928_4.